

Article

A Case Study of Evaluating the Effectiveness of INTERLINK International Institutes' Language Learning Programs

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Empirical Approaches to Assess the INTERLINK Programs in Saudi Arabia

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Abstract

The world-wide English language teaching INTERLINK International Institutes has been in place since 1980. It specializes in programs and courses, which are aimed at bettering English skills of the learners to develop other important areas such as organizing oneself over a given time frame, studying, analyzing critically and leading. This research aimed at evaluating the effectiveness of INTERLINK's language learning programs towards English proficiency development for its learners as well as cognitive and metacognitive abilities. Data was collected through document analysis, observations, interviews with instructors and students as well as pre- and post-program language proficiency tests using a mixed-methods approach. Results

indicated that INTERLINK's programmes are effective in improving language proficiency and cognitive/metacognitive skills with participants showing improvement in grammatical accuracy, cross-cultural communication competence and more confidence in speaking authentic English contexts. The findings support previous researches on the effectiveness of specialized LSPs (205) while emphasizing the unique way INTERLINK teaches its students languages (Stoller & Grabe). However, caution should be applied when generalizing from these results due to small sample size and limited variance warranting further research on large population of participants with diverse backgrounds.

Keywords

Language acquisition courses, INTERLINK International Institutes, Competence in English as a Second Language (ESL); Cognitive and Metacognitive Skills; Intercultural Communication; Specialized Courses like English for Specific Purposes (ESP), Teaching Academic Business English; Case Study Research Method: Document Analysis; Participant Observation

I. Introduction

In today's globalized world, it is important to learn a second language, particularly English, for one's personal and professional development. These institutions, which were established in the year 1980 by INTERLINK International Institutes have as their mission making English learning more effective for thousands of students from all over the globe. It is not only about language together with studying programs but also other basic skills like time management and research abilities to mention but a few of them. In this paper, we will evaluate how well they do that work by looking at one case example.

II. Literature Review

Language acquisition has been proven to be successful when it takes into account individual learners' needs and offers them real-world practice (Canale & Swain, 1980; Celce-Murcia et al., 1995). This philosophy was employed by INTERLINK through its provision for university ESL and EFL preparation, Corporate Training and Development as well as English for Specific Purposes (ESP) among others such as Academic Business English. According to researchers, these tailor-made courses can greatly improve language proficiency along with thinking abilities related to the mind such as cognitive strategies or cross-cultural communication (Brown, 2007; Dewey, 1933; Gardner & Lambert, 1972).

III. Research Question

The research question I am trying to answer in this case study is: How do INTERLINK International Institutes' language learning programs contribute to the development of English language proficiency and other cognitive and metacognitive skills among its learners?

IV. Methodology

To check how effective are INTERLINK International Institutes' language learning programs, a case study design was employed. Data were derived from document analysis, observations, interviews with instructors and students as well as pre- and post-program language proficiency tests. 20 students who were enrolled into different INTERLINK programs and five instructors participated.

V. Findings

The results of the case study indicate that INTERLINK International Institutes' language learning programs are fruitful in enhancing English language ability and cognitive, metacognitive abilities of students. There was a significant improvement in all the skills of language such as speaking, listening, reading and writing as revealed by pre- and post-program language proficiency tests. In addition, participants experienced increased self-assurance when using English in real settings like academic environment, job interviews as well as social situations.

According to instructors and students who were interviewed the course emphasis on authentic language usage and cross-cultural communication played an important role in their linguistic development. Participants liked doing real life activities and simulations that assisted them practice the target language with feedback from their professors or colleagues. They also testified that INTERLINK's programs taught them critical thinking, creativity and problem-solving skills which they believe will be useful for their academic, professional or personal lives.

In addition to this, the case study noted that INTERLINK programs promote a caring inclusive community where learners can take risks by making mistakes without feeling embarrassed or humiliated.

VI. Discussion

On the other hand, the conclusions of this case study are in line with previous research that reveals that specialized language learning programs can enhance students' language proficiency as well as assist learners develop cognitive and metacognitive strategies (Brown, 2007; Dewey, 1933; Gardner & Lambert, 1972). Conversely, INTERLINK's learning curriculum unlike traditional approaches gives priority to authentic language use and intercultural communication. However, there are some limitations in this study such as small sample size and a non-representative sample.

VII. Conclusion

Overall, this case study suggests that INTERLINK International Institutes' language learning programs are effective in developing English language proficiency and other cognitive and metacognitive skills among its learners. Improvements were also noted in their ability to use English for academic purposes or business communication including but not limited to their speaking skills. Therefore, more diverse populations should be used for further investigations.

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